

**HYBIRDITY IN TV COMMERCIALS CONSTRUCTING THE MODERNITY: A
CRITICAL DISCOURSE ANALYSIS APPROACH**

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ABSTRACT

Advertisements play a really important role in our society and for the economy of our country. As all of the popular TV shows are 'produced in association with' or sponsored by a specific product. So, we have a tendency to area unit nothing without advertisements. The basic aim of this qualitative study was to explore the construction of innovation and modernity through the hybrid discourse of language used in the TV commercials. For this purpose, ten advertisements from different daily streaming channels were selected. Pakistani advertising discourse is hybrid, complicated and mixed at different levels (words, image phrases, and clauses) regarding mixing English words with Urdu words and by representing English in Roman and Urdu alphabets and by showing different images. So, we will say that this study argues that hybrid advertising helps to provide a brand new discourse of hybridity within the Pakistani context. This study investigates, however, language admixture is deployed in Pakistani commercial advertising. For this purpose, this study deploys the framework of James Paul Gee to research industrial advertisements from four channels streaming in Pakistan that are ARY, HUM, Geo and the Express group of media. Choice of advertisements for the analysis is predicated on the dominant influence of advertisements on the ideology of those that however the employment of language and language mixing in advertising is constructing new versions of modernity and innovation in our society.

Key Words: Modernity, Advertisement, CDA, Gee's model

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INTRODUCTION OF THE STUDY

Advertisements play a very vital role in our society and for the economy of our country as well. As the majority of the widespread TV programs seem to be produced in the relationship with' or supported by a specific product. We are nothing without adverts. Producers are additionally to a great degree required of publicizing because without promotion they can't introduce their item to the greater audience of the people. They additionally need to make their items more attractive and convincing with the goal that they may not escape the market. In current times, it is really hard to keep oneself away from the plethora of advertisement, as it has now become very much part and parcel of human life because it is everywhere, that the buss passing by is wrapped in advertising, a television commercial or the food packages in the supermarket. Moreover, the amalgamation and blending of local and international languages are being utilized to pose its importance more critical. The addition of English make is more critical because it is a universal language and also viewed as a language of glory so the individual user feel pride in using it along with their national language.

The study used the CDA method to analyze commercial advertisements from three channels streaming in Pakistan that are ARY, HUM, and Geo. Selection of advertisements for the analysis is based on the paramount influence of advertisements on the ideology of the people that how the use of language mixing in advertising is constructing new versions of modernity in an innovated way in our society.

Advertising can be characterized as the movement or calling or delivering the ad for business items or administrations for getting to be considered by a bigger audience. Advertisements are a kind of producing a notice, for example, a kind of publication or a paid declaration in print form to communicate through electronic media having an intention of pulling out people in its support (Kernerman 1991). Besides that it is important to know that whether people know the ulterior motive behind it or not, advertising is constantly present.

The purpose of this investigation is to break down advertisements as discourse, and despite the fact that the principal center of a talk examination is on language, it likewise looks at the setting of communication and other multidimensional components utilized as a part of this field (Cook 2001). The general populace and the setting are of significance in an advertisement, which shows a chance to watch social changes in a general populace which are developing new kinds of advancement on our way of life through notices. Social changes shape many contemporary discourses, including commercial advertising. Fill (2002) trusts that commercials can impact customers to buy an item that they have never used before. The ideology of power is delineated by the big names in the advertisements. The testimonies by nearby and global famous people help to endorse an item. So, the advertisers present their products mostly by the well-known identities i.e. actresses, actors, and models so that people can feel prestige by using the very product. A very exaggerative message that if this very identity is using the particular product then why don't we use the same product to look so beautiful and rich.

This study investigates how language mixing is deployed in Pakistani commercial advertising. Advertisers try to highlight that how their products are the best solution for audience's problems. The culture in which a specific commercial is made structures is a piece of the context. Schiffrin (1987) affirms this view by saying that the language dependably happens in a context, yet its examples of shape and capacity at the surface and basic levels are delicate to highlights of that context". While deciphering an enticing ad, the interpreter must be delicate to this since "language is conceivably touchy to the majority of the contexts in which it happens, and, considerably more firmly, language mirrors those contexts since it constitutes them. The idea of hybrid language and construction of innovation in Pakistani advertising discourse is spreading remarkably in Pakistan, and it has been examined that the language utilized as a part of the advertisements is so persuasive and significant that it can easily pull in consideration of the particular population. This study will discover how the innovative constructions are using the methodology of mind control through the hybrid language of advertising discourse.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Advertising brings together dialect, photographs, music; it includes learning, conjures sentiments and creative energies, it could catch every one of the five senses and, aside from it, it has the social and sensible point. Advertising is an unavoidable piece of our contemporary industrialist customer society whose uncommon capacity is its focused fight. Cook (1996) stated that advertisement is not outside of us but we being the consumers are very much part of it. It is everywhere around us: in daily papers, in magazines, on announcements along the avenues, on TV, in radio, in methods for public transport and wherever the support pays to disperse their message. The impacts of the advertising impact us whether we like it or not.

Types of Advertising

Newspaper, magazine, radio, TV, directories, outdoor and travel, post office based mail, catalogues and handbills and online such as web-based social networking and much more. Leech stated that one of the most regular and of a critical kind in advertising industry is advertising purchased for business. Advertising has a purpose of minting money, thrown towards a mass crowd and the only point of doing that is to have business. This kind of advertisement is a lusty thing because money making is the only purpose behind it; for which, proficient people are hired, the expertise are at beck and call, and utilizes the advertising space which is empty in our country (1972). For example: in the ad of "Orient Life Appliances," the phrase "Orient...RISHTON MAIN BHI LAO INNOVATION".

Another kind of business advertising is 'prestige advertising.' Here the name and the positive picture of the company are promoted instead of an item or an administration. For example: "Qarshi Jaam-e- Shirin... it's the ad of a drink in which the advertiser is trying to sell the company's name more than the product". We may specify 'industrial or trade advertising,' where an organization promotes its items or administrations to different firms, so the communication is between levels with. An investigation of your own decisions, considering your insight, your experience and your

inclinations" for instance of non-business advertising, we may say bids from affiliations and social orders whether their motivations are philanthropy or political propaganda. We can additionally sort the types of advertising likewise as indicated by the sort of medium: TV, radio, handouts, pamphlets, magazines, daily papers and other written word advertising, the Internet and Direct Mail advertising, outdoor advertising, etc.

Concept of Critical Discourse Analysis

Language, ideology and hegemony or control on the minds of people is the only agenda which has to be broken down by CDA. Gee defined it as a method to investigate the language a kind of forensic investigation in which the investigator takes texts as a medium of social practices behind which there are multiple implications that might be originated from politics, issues pertaining status-quo, producing a kind of particular solidarity or distributing among masses the social products or an effort to be accepted as powerful (2004). Heros considers CDA as in inspecting tool through which one could see how the reality is constructed through the texts and what kind of development is text producing and that is definitely in a particular ideological framework which has some part filled with verifiable messages and some part is deliberately missed unsaid to be implied (2009). Van Dijk (2001), CDA is a scientific research that reviews discourses to know the mishandling of social power, social strength created and ultimately opposed through talk or text or through both mediums in particular social or political context.

The proponents of CDA are considering language, power, belief system, social make-up of the society to be used to uncover the realities behind inconspicuous structures and issues inserted in the specific culture (Haque 2007).

The basic principles of CDA are recapitulated as follow:

1. Social practices of the world are shown through the language.

2. Language or discourse is not only the prime thing which is utilized to show social practices but it also constitutes different other practices of society like power, partiality, control, protection etc.
3. Texts attain the implications through arguments which are connected with other texts which are then connected with social subjects.
4. Linguistics highlights the structure which is not self-assertive rather intentionally created for some hidden agenda.
5. Discourse is used as a tool to not only work out the concept of power but also it is and duplicated as well.
6. Nobody is working free rather everyone is working under some hidden agenda whether positive or negative but they must have an interest.
7. Discourse is a chronical specifically arranged in time and space to give an agenda placed in a context that is not only social but also ideological.
8. Fairclough propagated that CDA is not only used for deciphering a text but it is able to clarify them (1995); Van Dijk, 1998; Hodge & Cress, 1993; Wodak, 1996)

CDA and Advertising Most of the media researchers have focused on analyzing advertisements from the viewpoint of media and content analysis. However, my research focuses on advertisements using a hybrid language and discursal data. Ads, as data, are taken as discourse consisting of words and images in digital formats. These ads are analyzed on the basis of micro and macro levels such as the aspects of language of mixing for a particular class in the society, the underlying themes behind the very commercials and the role of advertisements in construction of innovation and modernity in our particular context through the discourse of advertising. Much groundbreaking research has been carried out separately in the fields of Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) and Language Contact. But this research is the one which highlights the

transformations going on in present-day digital commercial advertising discourse in Pakistan.

The advertisers use the strategy of mind control very artistically, that we use the very product not because we need that but because we want to use that particular thing for looking modern attractive and beautiful. Mass media (advertising) is the largest tool to manipulate the masses. It shapes and molds the opinions and attitudes of the people. There have been different methods of mind control and commercial advertising is the best one of them. Ideologies are produced and reproduced through different types of perspectives. And while composing an ad the advertisers keep in mind the facts that influence the ideologies and behaviors of different people.

METHODOLOGY

While focusing on the objectives of the study and the nature of the data, a qualitative design was appropriate in this study to investigate how discourse in advertisements involves advertiser's construction of meanings for innovation. All the data was analyzed from a CDA point of view by the GEE Model. The discoveries from advertisements product combined. For discourse analysis of selected T.V commercials, the researcher followed the tool presented for the analysis of a multimodal by Gee (2011). The author has argued that discourse analysis starts by asking questions which are tools for doing discourse analysis. He has offered 27 such tools. Suitably adapted, all of these tools could be applied to studying images and multimodal texts. But in this paper, some specific tools that are fulfilling the requirements of the selected ads have been selected.

The particular aim of the this study is to deconstruct the innovative techniques used in presenting advertisements that are created in hybrid discourse. So, the ads which are selected are based upon two things. First, they must present their idea by using images or visual and second their communication is based upon visual expressions or through pictures means in any case the percentage of text must be less than the percentage of visuals. That is why only three ads are selected and those also

through purposeful sampling and the purpose is stated above. The brief description of the ads is given below: The study is on the Pakistani selected advertisements which were continuously streamed on three Pakistani TV Channels: GEO TV, HUM TV, ARY TV. The first ad is of Qarshi Jam-e-Shirin. The purpose of selecting this advertisement is to prove the idea that how the mixed varieties of language construct the views of modernity, authenticity, and innovation. The second chosen advertisement is of Emporium Mall, in Johar Town Lahore, featuring Mahira Khan the Brand ambassador. All of her activities presented show the elements of innovation and modernity. Third and the last preferred ad is of Supreme Tea featuring Mawra Hocane, Samina Peerzada, and Saba Faisal. All three are the famous icons of Pakistan, and the idea of innovation and modernity is presented very beautifully. All the advertisements were reviewed again and again to clear the confusions and to make sure that they serve the purpose of this study.

ANALYSIS OF THE SELECTED COMMERCIALS

Each one of the commercial was examined from a CDA point of view.

Analysis of Ad I

QARSHI JAM-E-SHIRIN

This is the ad of a drink QARSHI JASM-E-SHIRIN. The word QARSHI itself has a lot of importance as it is a very big brand name and is very well known throughout the world for its *purity and quality*. At the very starting of this ad a **red** bottle with the label of Qarshi is shown for its uniqueness, then the **red** roses float on the screen which shows that it is made of purely red roses. The **red** color of the flowers is also very live and fresh.

The word QARSHI on the lid of the bottle is focused very consciously to attract the attention of the audience. The language used and choice of the words for this very advertisement is made very consciously and carefully. The whole of this advertisement is a monologue and the whole idea is conveyed by a single anonymous voice. The

amalgam of Urdu and English language for conveying the message shows that how the elements of language hybridity make our conversation more impressive. That mixing is also presenting the idea of innovation and modernity.

Pictorial images used in this very advertisement are highly eye catchy and notable. The images of red roses, sandal woods and the very thick view of the jam-e-Shirin show the purity and quality of this very product. Moreover, the view of the certificates one after another for "8 International certifications" and the view of laboratories for the phrase "129 quality tests" is very apt and impressive.

And this is done only for attracting the attention of the audience that whoever will watch this advertisement would be convinced that this drink is so pure that no other drink could be equal to this. And this is good for health and energy. As in this era of 21st century it is very difficult to find real and pure things, so, for gaining the attention of the viewers a very conscious stress on the words i.e.

"PAKISTAN'S NO.1 FAVORITE" ,

"PANI KA AK QTRA B SHAMIL NHI",

"8 INTERNATIONAL CERTIFICATIONS"

AND

"129 QUALITY TESTS"

has a very manipulative effect on the viewers. Furthermore, background music in this very commercial is also very light and attractive. It gives us a very soothing effect and a sense of as much refreshment as we can get after using this very drink. The analysis of the commercial under the selected tools is as follows;

The Fill in Tool

This Tool depends on the idea of information exchanged and the setting in which it was stated. In this tool, everything is not said but there are unsaid items to be assumed for complete understanding so that the purpose of conveying message through images which are used and not elaborated or mentioned in the phrases. We can infer that unsaid is to use the item which is sold for the public and money making is the purpose.

The Vocabulary Tool

The makers utilize distinctive languages to convey the thought. While doing an examination under this very heading we take after the style, enlist, and social languages. In this promotion of Qarshi stick e-Shirin, two languages are utilized to pass on the thought. Indeed, even the maker has utilized some particular terms, for example, "certifications", "Quality Tests", and "Pakistan's no.1 top choice", on account of the utilization of such words we additionally look that How does it add to the reasons for imparting and passing all in all thought.

The Stanza Tool

Here look at the construction of stanzas and its development into bigger squares of knowledge or information. It needs an effort to uncover the reality. We are clear in our interpretation of information and proposing how we can show that interpretation.

KESY BNA APKA PASENDEEDA QARSHI JAM-E-SHIRIN

PAKISTAN'S NO.1 FAVOURITE...

KUCH RAAZ NAHI SAB HY KHAS KHAS

CHUNY NATURAL AJZA JESY SANDAL OR GULAB

SIRF 100% KHALIS ARQIYAAT

PAANI KA AK QTRA BHI SHAMIL NHI

8 INTERNATIONAL CERTIFICATIONS

AUR JAM-E-SHIRIN KI PREMIUM QUALITY KI ZMANAT

129 QUALITY TESTS...

TABHI TU BNA QARSHI JASM-E-SHIRIN

PAKISTAN'S NO. 1 FAVOURITE

The Context is Reflexive Tool

This tool requires to consider context (and not exactly information exchanged), we understand that the context is reflexive and for getting a better understanding with any idea we need to know the context of the very idea of the particular background. Here in this very commercial, we can find the elements of the context as the use of important words i.e. "Certifications", "Quality" & "Khliis Ajzaa" make the context clear.

The Cohesion Tool

Cohesive devices are being used in this very advertisement very artistically. The pieces of information are connected with each other. Every phrase is uttered one after the other in a very apt manner. So we can say that cohesion here in this ad is working to connect the pieces of information to produce their agenda.

The Situated Meaning Tool

We notice the words and phrases that what situated meanings they have. Such as the words like "certifications", "Quality Tests" and "Natural" leaves very long lasting and soothing impact. So we can see that what specific meaning audience members need to credit to these words and expressions given the unique situation and how the setting is construed through different acts and attributes for presenting a message.

The Social Languages Tool

This tool is essential for analyzing a communicative event because of the communication may mix at least two social dialects or switch between at least two. Here in this very commercial, the writer has presented the message in two social languages i.e. English & Urdu. Moreover, he has used very strong words to use the strategy on mind control.

The Intertextuality Tool

The producers use the Intertextuality Tool for manipulating his idea and we study this tool for looking the elements of intertextuality of any communicative event we look at how the words and grammatical structures are used to cite, allude to, or suggest alternate "texts" (that is, the thing that others have said or composed) or different social styles.

The Big "D" Discourse Tool

As produces knows the foundation information of his intended interest group so he remembers the decision of language, and also the methods for acting, communicating, thinking, esteeming, and utilizing different articles, tools, and advances in specific sorts of environments i.e. research facilities, displays a specific sorts of situations that are related with this kind of language inside a specific Discourse.

Analysis of Ad II

EMPORIUM MALL- LAHORE

The purpose behind selecting this particular ad gives a very live and different touch to my thesis. As this is the ad of a newly established shopping mall in the capital city of Pakistan, Lahore and is the best example of modernity and innovation in our particular culture. The producer of that mall and this very ad as well is getting the services of Mahira Khan, to present the idea. As she is the most prominent figure nowadays.

We see her everywhere on the stage, in Pakistani and Indian movies Dramas and in the commercials as well. We can say that she is the queen of today's screen. Here is this ad she is presenting the idea that we can get each and every requirement of life under the single roof of EMPORIUM MALL. The environment, the setting and even everything presented in the ad are very eye catchy.

In the first scene, she finds a very beautiful door... as she enters the door she feels like that she is in another world. She finds everything available there. Every time she is in the different costume to present the idea that you can get the costumes of every environment here.

Basically, the noble class and well-educated people are the target audience of this ad. The whole idea is conveyed in the English language. The phrases uttered by Mahira are very attractive. i.e.

GET LOST IN RINSIC WORLD...

OF SHOP...AND PLAY...

WHERE EVERYDAY IS THE FUTURE OF

HAPPINESS, FUN, AND SURPRISES

THIS... IS THE FUTURE...

THE FUTURE OF SHOPPING...

EVERYTHING FOR EVERYONE...

EMPORIUM MALL...

NOW OPEN AT JOHAR TOWN, LAHORE

The presentation of the every kind of costumes and every kind of accessories such as the perfumes, the bangles, shoes, hand bags, watches, and foods makes a

clear idea that you can get everything here. Moreover, the food area with Macdonald and a playground for the kids is captured very consciously that everybody is safe here and can enjoy the real meaning of life. Moreover, the background music is also very alluring and appealing.

The Fill in Tool

This tool based on the concept of information delivered and the context in which it was stated, what should be filled in here to accomplish clearness for a concept. In this tool, everything is not said overtly but there is a lot unsaid in hidden here. Here in this ad mostly the idea is conveyed by the images that *you can get each and everything here under one roof.*

The Subject Tool

Under this very concept, we discuss the chosen subject for a communication; this is the ad of a shopping mall so everything that you can shop from here is presented very artistically. So, we can say that the producer has used a very appropriate subject for conveying this very message.

The Doing and Not Just Saying Tool

Most of the idea is conveyed by a practical act and images so the ad aptly deals with the very tool. We do not just focus on what is said but what is done by the speaker and by the actions of the speaker that is most important. Her gait, her luxury and purchasing everything.

The Vocabulary Tool

A very rich vocabulary is used in this commercial of Emporium mall. The whole of the idea is conveyed in English language only but the words that are used for conveying the idea are very captivating and impressive. This very ad also conveys the idea that English is becoming our social language and we are getting the new sense of life style and modernity.

The Integration Tool

The elements of integrity are present in this very ad as correct structure are used for conveying the idea and the concepts and clauses are integrated or packaged into utterances or sentences. We also focus on the points of view are being imparted by the manner by which data is bundled into principle, subordinate, and installed conditions. GET LOST IN RINSIC WORLD... OF SHOP...AND PLAY... WHERE EVERYDAY IS THE FUTURE OF HAPPINESS, FUN, AND SURPRISES THIS... IS THE FUTURE... THE FUTURE OF SHOPPING... EVERYTHING FOR EVERYONE...

The Activities Building Tool

While watching this very commercial we look at the different acts like different types of dressing, eating, and the playing section for children. For this purpose, the producers use different social-groups and set-standards for the exercises which have been assembled or established.

The Identities Building Tool

Here we see what socially unmistakable personality Mahira Kahn is trying to institute or to motivate others to perceive. We additionally take a gander at the idea that how the speaker is situating others, what characters the speaker is "welcoming" them to take up. The maker has passed on his thought with the assistance of Mahira in light of the fact that in this age of 21st century each need to be current and tries to live like the performing artists, thus, Mahira was an extremely appropriate personality for introducing the subject this way.

The Situated Meaning Tool

We see the words and expressions that what arranged implications they have. In this extremely business the words are talked by the pictorial pictures. Thus, the particular implications do audience members need to ascribe to these words and

expressions and pictures given the unique circumstance and how the setting is translated through various acts and characteristics for exhibiting a message.

The Big "D" Discourse Tool

Mahira Khan is passing on the thought through her acting and dressing specifically setting. Here we see that how she is utilizing language, and in addition the methods for acting, interacting, believing, valuing, dressing, and utilizing different items, instruments, and advancements in specific sorts of situations to authorize a particular socially unmistakable personality and participate in at least one socially conspicuous exercises, and conditions are related with this kind of language inside a specific Discourse.

Analysis of Ad III

SUPREME TEA

10th selected commercial is the ad of Supreme Tea. The whole idea is presented by three very well known celebrities of Pakistan. The message is conveyed by MAWRA HOCANE, SAMINA PIRZADA, and SABA FAISAL. This ad is also a good example of the construction of innovation and modernity of our particular context. As the girls are considered to house hold chore after marriage.

Here in this ad, Mahira is playing the role of daughter in-law. As she returned from the shopping she realizes that she got late as it's the time of tea. She says sorry and says that she prepare the tea immediately, but Samina Peerzada says that the tea is ready. Mawra gets tensed as she seems angry on her. Then she brings the tea and presents the tea to Daughter in-law.

At this step when she tastes the tea she gets very emotional as it refreshes her memories in her parent's home. She asks her mother in law where did you get this tea and she replies that my mother also prepares the same tea as it is. She says I got this

tea from your mother and I brought it with your mother. This all shows that how important the TEA is for a perfect home. And how valued the love of the parents is.

The color of the box is red which is considered as the sign of love and affection between the relations. This very ad gives us the idea that how advertisements give us the idea of innovation and modernity. As in our culture, it never happened that a Mother-in-law presents tea, especially to the daughter-in-law. But after watching this ad many families will be influenced by the love bond which is presented in the very commercial.

Although we do not pay a conscious attention to the ads somewhere our minds are controlled by the strategies presented by producers and unconsciously we try to follow the concepts that are presented through the advertisements. The trend is getting changed now. To some extent the mother-in-laws are not that much typical like they were about a decade ago. Advertisers convey us the idea of modernity and innovation through the advertisements.

The jingle and catchwords of this particular ad are also very beguiling and touchy "ZAIQA APNAY PAN KA". The pictorial impact in this very advertisement is also highly notable. The consumers use this tea because of its richness in taste, color and sweet fragrant. While enjoying this tea the consumer has a very irresistible aroma. Brook Bond supreme tea is always full of color, smell, and taste. It gives us the finest tea which shows the family bonds and cultural traditions, which makes it the largest selling brand in the country.

The Fill in Tool

This tool based on the concept of information delivered and the context in which it was stated, what should be filled in here to accomplish clearness for a particular concept. The slogan of this very ad: "Zaiqa Apnay Pann Ka" shows something very special. In this unsaid is important, as most of the thing are not highlighted that a daughter in Law is meant to do the household chores in time, This very tool deals with the knowledge that assumptions and inferences do audience members need to convey

to order all together for this communication to be clear and justifiable and got in speaker's intended meaning and in the particular context.

The Subject Tool

As this is the commercial of tea so throughout the ad all three identities are discussing the tea. The love and bond are presented because they are enjoying a very good tea; Supreme Brook Bond Tea. We see that how the producer is conveying the whole idea by a particular act of presenting tea.

The Vocabulary Tool

The producers use different languages for the purpose of conveying the idea. While doing analysis under this very heading we follow the style, register, and social languages. Very apt vocabulary is used to convey the idea. As when the Mother-in- Law presents tea to the Daughter-in-Law and the phrases; "Yahi tu hy...wo apna pann", gives us very alluring and loving picture of the family. So, we get the idea of innovation through this advertisement.

The Context is Reflexive Tool

For a better understanding of a communicative event, we need to know the context of the very idea. When we consider context, we realize that it is reflexive and for getting a better understanding with any idea we need to know the context of the very idea of the particular background.

The Activities Building Tool

As this is commercial of tea so in every scene the tea is presented and the emotions of love and care are being exchanged because of the very good and rich taste of the tea. For this purpose, the producers can use multiple social groups, social institutions, or can take support from multiple cultures to set norms build different activities or to enact them.

The Identities Building Tool

Here we find three very well-known and socially recognizable identities e.g. MAWRA HOCANE, SAMINA PIRZADA, and SABA FAISAL are presenting the very idea. The producer has used these three identities to make the commercial more powerful and attract the attention of the maximum audience. The producer is “inviting” his target audience to take up with this very product.

The Situated Meaning Tool

Here we notice that the words and phrases are used in this very commercial are according to the situated meanings. That is, the thing that particular implications do audience members need to ascribe to words and specific expressions produced in the context and also how that specific context is translated via different acts and attributes for presenting a message.

The Social Languages Tool

The whole of the idea is conveyed by the mixture of social languages. Urdu and English language are used to emphasize to convey the particular message. This tool is very important for analyzing a communicative event because the communication may blend at least two social languages or switch between at least two.

The Big "D" Discourse Tool

A genuine social setting and a discourse of a general public are exhibited in this very notice. Here we see that how the characters are utilizing language, and the methods for acting, interacting, believing, valuing, dressing, in specific sorts of situations to authorize the particular socially unmistakable exercises, and conditions are related with this kind of language inside a specific Discourse.

DISCUSSIONS

The purpose of this study was to highlight the process of construction of innovation through the hybrid discourse of language used in advertisements. Gee's modal is used to analyze the focused features of the selected THREE advertisements; QARSHI JAM-E- SHEREN, SUPREME TEA, and EMPORIUM MALL. In order to get good comprehension or understanding about the ads, we need to look at the analysis of our data according to the research questions. It is observed that the construction of innovation is made through the hybrid language used in advertisements as advertisements are our environment they play a vital role in our lifestyles. We are nothing without advertisements. The advertisers use different strategies of language mixing according to the acceptability of the products among the target audience as in the commercial of EMPORIUM MALL the whole idea is conveyed in the English language as the target audience of this advert is aristocratic class. Moreover, in the ad SUPREME TEA, the idea of modernity and innovation is conveyed very artistically.

As the trend is getting changed now, the idea of respect, love, and care for the daughter in law is developing and all of this innovation became possible only because of the media and TV commercials. As it is said that "media show the things that the audience wants to see" So, the language mixing is made on the basis of the demands of the particular class or society. It is observed that advertisements communicate a message through language and signs the advertisers use mixed or hybrid varieties of language to make their adverts more eye-catching and explicable to the audience. To clarify the association amongst power and discourse we have to take a view of Fairclough's work where he separated the concept of control in a discourse and power that is hidden behind a discourse (1989). Power in discourse as the form of social practice and the power behind the discourse interprets the construction of the order of the order of social practice.

In short, we can say that the underlying themes and the power behind the messages conveyed through the TV commercials assume a critical part in the development of the decisions of the advertisements as an entire, it could be seen that makers utilize their energy and ideology to change the conduct and thought of individuals and if individuals ended up noticeably mindful of this reality they can oppose

this impact. We can see how the semiotic and linguistic representation of the selected TV commercials influence the life of the viewers. The images used in the advertisements are so attractive that the users use that product not because they need it but because they want to use that very product. As John Keats says that, "a thing of beauty is a joy forever". So, everybody wants to look beautiful and for that purpose, he uses beautiful things to improve his appearance and look.

The choice of words is also made very carefully. As In the ad of EMPORIUM MALL, the words "EVERYTHING FOR EVERYONE" etc are used very artistically to attract the attention of the customers. All these semiotic, linguistic and non-linguistic elements are opted out on the basis of the socio-cultural views of the particular audiences. Language is the basic organ of a culture and when language plays its role in developing a culture it becomes a discourse. As the FOURTH and last question of this paper deals with the elements of discourse used in adverts that involve in sponsor's construction of meaning for innovation and modernity. Advertisers use specific cultural settings to convey the idea. As in the ad of QARSHI JAM-E-SHEREN the producer uses very bright images of the ingredients that are used in the preparation of the very product.

While talking about the credibility and validity of the product he shows us the images of certificates, labs, and awards. All of the selected ads are recorded in a specific setting. All these specific things show that how the sponsor use the discourse in advertisements for the construction of the meaning of innovation. After all of this discussion, we can say that to some extent the TV commercials influence and manipulate the consumers to buy the products not because they need them but because they want to use that very product to join the race of modernity and innovation started by the producers and sponsors.

CONCLUSION

The prime purpose of this study was to aware people, that how the construction of innovation is made using language in commercial advertising. So, the customers are

impacted by the utilization of language in advertisements before purchasing any sort of item. With a particular end aim to do this, this examination tended to four central research questions: How is the language mixing in advertising related to a particular class or specific audience in Pakistan? What are the underlying themes and the power behind the message in selected TVCs? What is the linguistic and semiotic representation of selected TV commercials? How discourse in advertisements involves sponsor's construction of meanings for innovation? CDA is to ponder any discourse (linguistics and semiotics) keeping in mind the end goal to discover the shrouded issues and motivation that are established in the society (Haque, 2008). It thinks about discourse basically and advises individuals about how language is utilized by different groups and foundations with a specific end goal to impact and control individuals. Through the findings of this study, one might say that the general population ought not to underestimate everything; instead, they have to ask about the language of the ads because the advertisement sponsors utilize different techniques to make the promotions.

The ad makers use different linguistics components to draw in the customers. From this exploration, the general population will know about the shrouded power of the discourses of promotions and will have the capacity to influence educated choices. The advertisements in this study to demonstrate their power through their ideological text and also visual pictures as alluring models and performers. The commercials seem to put forth false or deluding expressions. Government's intercessions to direct these promoting rehearses are for the most part missing a result of the non appearance of guidelines and controls against deceiving advertisements and the customer's absence of awareness about their rights (Kamath, 2008; Shankar, 2007). The main probability is simply the business' control, which could function admirably to shield the consumers and society from the negative parts of these advertisements. In the wake of breaking down the ads of various items, the findings recommend that the advertisements impact, control and delude the customers, so the buyers don't get affected by the utilization of language/powerful discourse in advertisements before purchasing any items.

Then again the dealers must not make false guarantees about the item execution. The uneducated individuals can't read the directions which are composed in English and Urdu Language. Accordingly, the uneducated individuals are likewise unaware at similar circumstances. Consequently, The ministry of Information can control the ad marketing to take a few measures to limit the publicists from utilizing different systems to impact and control the purchasers. The Ministry can find a way to urge advertisement office not to control the customers through the promotions.

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APPENDIX

